

CN⁻), Ni²⁺ (25, masked by 1% CN⁻), Co²⁺ (25, masked by 1% CN⁻), Cu²⁺ (20, masked by 1% CN⁻), Pb²⁺ (10, masked by EDTA), Mo⁶⁺ (40), W⁶⁺ (40), U⁶⁺O₈ (20), V⁵⁺ (20, masked by 1% CN⁻), Cd²⁺ (20), Hg²⁺ (20) and Ag⁺ (10, masked by EDTA).

Determination of zinc in milk samples: Dry ashing method⁶ was used in determining the zinc contents of milk. Milk (25 ml) was added dropwise to a heated crucible to evaporate without forthing and after removal of moisture it was heated strongly to 450-500°. Concentrated nitric acid (1 ml) was added after cooling. It was then evaporated to dryness and ignited again at 450-500° for ~ 1h. Care was taken to avoid loss by sputtering. The resulting white ash was dissolved in the minimum amount of dilute nitric acid and made up to 25 ml in a standard flask. To the aliquot (1 or 2 ml), was added 0.1% KCN solution (0.5 ml) to mask the interfering metals and then 1% formaldehyde (1 ml) was added and zinc was determined by the recommended procedure.

Recovery of zinc from milk samples: The standard milk samples were spiked by adding known amounts of zinc and the total zinc was determined with the reagent. Table 1 reports the recovery data obtained with QATB and confirms the precision of the method. It was noted that zinc contents were variable in samples taken from different animal and breed, as well as time of the lactation process. Another factor of variation might be dependent upon the feed, age and health of the animal. It was also noticed that milk samples kept overnight in galvanised utensils have slightly higher zinc contents, which may be due to contamination of zinc during pasteurisation.

TABLE 1—RESULTS AND RECOVERY DATA FOR ZINC IN VARIOUS MILK SAMPLES WITH QATB AS REAGENT*

Milk samples	Zn ²⁺ found μg ml ⁻¹	Zn ²⁺ added μg ml ⁻¹	Zn ²⁺ recovered μg ml ⁻¹	Range of % recovery
Cow	3.67, 3.52, 3.81, 4.07	2.8	6.67, 6.12, 6.48, 6.80	96.83–103.09
Buffalo	2.98, 3.28, 3.06, 3.25	2.8	5.90, 6.05, 5.63, 5.83	96.08–102.99
Goat	3.84, 4.09, 3.57, 4.02	2.8	6.86, 7.02, 6.45, 6.72	98.97–103.31
Govt. supply (skimmed milk)	4.15, 3.90, 4.20, 4.08	2.8	6.70, 6.93, 6.80, 6.98	96.40–103.42

* Number of analyses = 4.

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Rapid Method for the Determination of Coking Value of some Carbonaceous Materials

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THE coking value is a measure of the amount of carbon (coke) left on heating a sample of carbonaceous materials, like tar, pitch and similar products, under specified conditions. The coking value is generally determined by Conradson carbon method¹. A simple, convenient and elegant method has been developed by the authors in this laboratory.

Experimental

The apparatus very similar to that used for proximate analysis of coal can be employed in the present method. The muffle furnace in addition to having rapid heat regaining capacity, should have an arrangement to exclude air circulation inside the furnace during the experiment. It is worth mentioning that heating may be done either by gas or electricity. A steady temperature of 570±5° should be maintained and sample heated for 7 min for the determination of coking value.

Accurately weighed sample (0.5-2.0 g) is taken in the silica crucible (specifications in Table 1). To

TABLE 1—SPECIFICATIONS OF THE SILICA CRUCIBLE* (DIMENSIONS IN MM)

Crucible	Lid
1. Height : 38	Internal dia. : 27
2. External dia. : 25	Dia. of well : 21
3. Internal dia. : 22	Depth of the well : 4
4. Combined weight of the crucible and lid should be between 12-14 gms.	
5. Maximum clearance between crucible and lid, at the top edge of the crucible should be 0.5 mm.	

*Crucible must be cylindrical, translucent, with a lid of capsule type.

this accurately weighed inert material (2-3 g), i.e. sand of specified grade², (Table 2), is mixed.

NOTES

TABLE 2—SPECIFICATIONS OF STANDARD SAND

The essential characteristics of the sand suitable for use in the determination of coking value should be as follows.

1. It should be completely inert and be of pure silica and should be free from impurities, such as clay, chalk and iron carbonates.
2. It should pass a 30 mesh IS sieve (BS-52) and be retained on 20 mesh IS sieve (BS-72).
3. It should not contain more than 5% oversize and or 10% undersize.
4. On heating for 3 h at 920°, the undersize produced by disintegration should not exceed 2.5%.
5. Its solubility in hot dilute hydrochloric acid should not exceed 0.5%.

Travancore sand as well as coke powder may be used as inert material. However, in this method, Travancore sand is chosen instead of coke powder because the latter may increase the percentage of coking value of the sample under test by coke/tar/volatile interaction^a. The quantity of sample to be taken for the determination of coking value is indicated in Table 3.

TABLE 3 - QUANTITY OF SAMPLE REQUIRED FOR COKING VALUE DETERMINATION

Sl. no.	Coking value %	Quantity of sample required g
1.	≤10	1.5 - 2.0
2.	10 - 30	1.0 - 1.5
3.	≥30	0.50 - 1.0

Fourteen samples having coking values 1.50 to 62.77% were subjected to the tests at four different temperatures, namely, 570, 620, 670 and 730°. From the results of the experiments (Table 4) it is seen that 570 ± 5° is the ideal temperature for carrying out the investigation.

TABLE 4 - RESULTS OF COKING VALUES AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES AND THEIR DIFFERENCE FROM CONRADSON CARBON

Sl. no.	Conradson carbon (A) % (w/w)	730° (B) % (w/w)	Diff. (A-B) % (w/w)	670° (C) % (w/w)	Diff. (A-C) % (w/w)	620° (D) % (w/w)	Diff. (A-D) % (w/w)	570° (E) % (w/w)	Diff. (A-E) % (w/w)
1.	62.77							64.00	-1.23
2.	58.16	50.52	-7.64	54.06	-4.10	54.46	-3.70	58.04	+0.12
3.	55.28	47.48	-7.80	50.26	-5.02	50.91	-4.37	53.57	+1.71
4.	52.75	44.13	-8.62	47.55	-5.20	47.32	-5.43	51.45	+1.30
5.	52.51	44.30	-8.21	48.41	-4.10	47.47	-5.03	51.88	+0.63
6.	52.14	45.09	-7.05	47.47	-4.67	48.18	-3.96	52.19	-0.05
7.	48.56	41.50	-7.06	43.40	-5.16	44.48	-4.08	48.64	-0.08
8.	34.32							33.27	+1.05
9.	32.20	29.25	-2.95	29.69	-2.51	31.67	-0.53	32.28	-0.08
10.	30.08							28.88	+1.20
11.	22.00	19.60	-3.04	23.60	-1.64	21.01	-0.99	20.52	+1.48
12.	11.61	9.31	-2.28	9.00	-2.61	10.12	-1.49	10.35	+1.26
13.	1.70							1.66	+0.04
14.	1.50							1.74	-0.24

Regarding the repeatability of the tests, duplicate determinations were carried out for a number of samples (Table 5). In all the determinations, the

TABLE 5—REPEATABILITY OF DUPLICATE DETERMINATIONS OF THE MODIFIED METHOD*

Sl. no.	I determination	II determination	Average	± % Deviation from average
1.	64.42	63.58	64.00	0.70
2.	52.04	52.34	52.19	0.20
3.	51.86	51.90	51.88	0.04
4.	51.60	51.30	51.45	0.30
5.	53.56	53.58	53.57	0.01
6.	72.90	71.66	72.28	0.86
7.	33.20	33.34	33.27	0.20
8.	29.45	28.31	28.88	2.00
9.	7.19	7.18	7.185	0.00
10.	20.13	20.91	20.52	1.80
11.	1.83	1.65	1.74	5.20
12.	1.71	1.62	1.66	2.40

* % variation of each determination from the average result.

results of successive tests were well within 2.4% of the average of the two tests.

Discussion

For the determination of coking value as described above, only common equipments which are necessary for proximate analysis of coal and coke are required. In the present method there is drastic reduction in time for the determination of coking value (Conradson method, ~ 1 h; present method, ~ 0.5 h).

In Conradson method heating is done by gas of calorific value of ~ 500 btu/ft³ which is sometimes difficult to generate in many laboratories; moreover, the rate of heating is controlled mainly by regulating the inflow of the gas in the burner, which involves personal error. Further, in Conradson carbon method, a time period of 30 ± 2 min must be observed even it is necessary to use different burner or gas to do so. It is to be noted, however,

TABLE 6—COKING VALUES OF SAMPLES DETERMINED BY CONRADSON CARBON METHOD USING DIFFERENT BURNERS AND GASES

Sl. no.	Burner	Gas	Sample No. 1 wt. %	Sample No. 2 wt. %	Sample No. 3 wt. %	Sample No. 5 wt. %	Sample Tar wt. %
1.	Gansen Burner	Cokeoven gas	86.00	89.80	80.37	78.30	56.10
		Cal gas (L.P.G.)	60.23	63.98	52.38	43.46	27.38
2.	Bunsen Burner	Cokeoven gas	55.52	57.21	48.86	42.10	25.05
		Cal gas (L.P.G.)	57.03	58.87	49.75	42.62	26.12
3.	Meker Burner	Cokeoven gas	55.60	58.67	50.05	42.40	25.51
		Cal gas (L.P.G.)	56.23	59.05	50.54	41.92	26.63

Coke oven gas—C.V. = ~500 Btu/ft³.
 Cal gas (L.P.G.)—C.V. = ~1150 Btu/ft³.

that the tolerance of variation of calorific value of the gas to be used as a heating medium, has not been mentioned in Conradson carbon method. In India, light petroleum gas (LPG) having high calorific value (~1150 Btu/ft³) is generally used as heating medium in different laboratories.

With a view to study the effect of using different gases having wide variation in calorific values as well as that of different burners, namely bunsen, meker, gansen (the new type of burner meant for LPG which is in use in India) *etc.* several experiments have been conducted for the determination of coking values of different pitch and tar samples by Conradson method using different burners and gases. The results of the experiments are shown in Table 6. There is definite limitation on the use of different types of burners as well as gases of different calorific values by the Conradson carbon method as is evident from the Table 6. The present method does not impose such stipulation either on the use of gas or on burners since the experiment is conducted at a particular coking temperature which may be achieved either by using gas or electricity.

It is interesting to observe that total time required for the determination of coking value is hardly 0.5 h for the present method. In contrast, coking value determination by Conradson method

requires at least 1h. Apart from the simplicity of apparatus and method of heating, this is an important parameter in industry since it helps determination of more samples in short period. The other methods employed for coking value determinations are Ramsbottom⁴, Norske and modified Norske⁵. Ramsbottom method is suitable for lubricating oils and distillate fuel oils. In Norske method, the time required for one determination is 6-7 h. Moreover, this method has not been tried for samples other than pitch having coking values ranging 40 to 50%.

Thus, it is evident from the foregoing discussion that the present method can be conveniently adopted for the determination of coking value of all types of carbonaceous materials since it has got several advantages.

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